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A methodology for the assessment of sealing joints in high-temperature SOFC stacks

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Abstract

High-temperature Solid Oxide Fuel Cells (SOFCs) enable an efficient and economical way to convert chemical energy, stored in fuels, directly into electrical energy. A decisive factor for the reliable long-term operability of the stack is the hermetic sealing and thus a separation of oxidant and fuel gas. The design of the sealing, commonly made of glass ceramics is very demanding since it has to withstand high temperature loadings. The load on the sealing results from the inhomogeneous temperature field and the mismatch of thermal expansion coefficients yielding an inhomogeneous stress field. Furthermore, time-dependent effects have to be considered as well. In the present work a methodology for the assessment of glass ceramic sealings is presented and applied to a recent SOFC design, developed by Forschungszentrum Jülich.

Using simplified two-dimensional models and where necessary a parameterized three-dimensional full scale finite element model, stationary in operation load cases as well as cooling down to ambient temperature are investigated.

Particular emphasis is placed on the discussion of the physical mechanisms causing stresses within the sealing. If the temperature is below the glass transition temperature, time-invariant material behavior may be postulated. Hence, crack initiation in the sealing yielding leakage may be predicted using the coupled stress and energy criterion within the framework of finite fracture mechanics. If the temperature is larger than the glass transition temperature viscoelastic behavior has to be taken into account. Finally, on the basis of sensitivity analyses possibilities for an improved design are discussed.

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Introduction

Solid Oxide Fuel Cells are operating in a temperature range from about 600°C to 1000°C. Due to the high operating temperatures, they allow solid ceramics, often yttria-stabilised zirconia, as cost-efficient electrolyte. Moreover, SOFCs exhibit energy conversion rates that exceed those of other fuel cell concepts [1]. Nevertheless, also difficulties associated with high operating temperatures arise. Especially for planar SOFC designs the hermetic sealing of the fuel cell stacks is challenging [2]. The seals are subjected to high operating temperatures, inhomogeneous temperature fields, and reactive atmospheres. Thus, the seals can significantly reduce the lifespan of the fuel cell stacks since even weak leakage can markedly affect the cell performance [3]. As a consequence, the sealing development plays a major role in a potential industrial SOFC application. Different sealing concepts were proposed. They can be roughly distinguished between compressive and rigid seals. A compressive seal is a compliant high temperature material that is placed between the sealing surfaces. The seal effect is reached by compressing the seal by external forces on the fuel cell top. That type of sealing is not materially bonded to the surfaces and therefore allows a relative movement between the sealing surfaces such that different thermal expansion behavior of the stack components can be handled. A drawback of that type of seals is that a certain leakage cannot be avoided, as shown by many authors.

More widespread is the concept of rigid seals since it exhibits several advantages. Typically, rigid seals consist of glasses or glass ceramics [4]. As a matter of principle, rigid seals avoid leakage effectively. The sealing has to fulfill several complex requirements in order to ensure proper SOFC operation. At the same time, it has to withstand thermal stresses caused by differences in coefficients of thermal expansion (CTEs) or temperature gradients, stresses induced by the stack weight or gas pressure, thermal cycling between ambient temperature and operating temperature, creeping and chemical reactions [4]. Due to the high relevance of rigid seals, numerous studies have been conducted. For an initial overview the interested reader is referred to [2, 4, 5].

However, the reliability of the sealing has a major impact on the lifespan of the SOFC stack. Hence, the failure assessment of seals comes to the fore. The mechanical properties of glass ceramics sealants change significantly depending on whether the temperature T is above or below the glass transition temperature T_g . Within the failure assessment this change has to be taken into account. Several authors proposed to operate the SOFC above the glass transition temperature of the sealant in order to reduce stresses that occur due to a CTE mismatch by means of viscosity [6, 7]. But there is evidence that creep damage may occur in the long run [8]. Below the glass transition temperature brittle material behavior is expected involving different failure modes. Typically, stress based criteria are used for the failure prediction. Due to the fact that the occurring stress fields are highly inhomogeneous particularly at the junction between the sealant and the adjacent metal layers, where a so-called free-edge effect occurs, classical strength-of-material approaches are not suitable.

As alternative approach, failure criteria based on linear elastic fracture mechanics (LEFM) were proposed. Those criteria require the existence of a pre-existing crack or inherent flaw. As a consequence, assumptions must be made regarding a fictitious crack size.

To surpass the mentioned limitations Leguillon [9] proposed a combination of the strength-of-material approach and linear elastic fracture mechanics in form of a coupled stress- and energy criterion.

In the present work, a methodology for the assessment of glass ceramics seals failure is proposed. Since the temperature during operation can be both above and below the glass transition temperature, both cases must be considered within the failure prediction.

The suggested procedure is explained using a current SOFC design developed by Forschungszentrum Jülich, but also using simple examples. Furthermore, the mechanisms

responsible for the occurrence of the stresses are investigated and their influence on the failure behavior is discussed.

1. Scientific Approach

In the following the methodology for the assessment of the glass-ceramics seals is discussed. As depicted in Fig.1 the failure assessment can first be classified according to the type of load.

Figure 1: Methodology for the investigation of glass-ceramics seal failure.

During its lifetime the SOFC stack is exposed to a variety of different loads as, for instance, cyclic loading due to the cool-down to room temperature and heat-up to the operating temperature, or the static stationary operation. In the following only the latter load case is considered. As previously mentioned, the failure behavior of the glass-ceramics depends on the temperature. Hence, within the failure assessment a distinction must be made whether the operating temperature is above or below the glass transition temperature.

Below the glass transition temperature brittle fracture occurs. If the stress field is homogeneous a classical stress based criterion is suitable for failure prediction. Generally, highly inhomogeneous stress fields are expected for SOFCs since the temperature field in operation behaves also inhomogeneously and differences in the coefficients of thermal expansions between the involved materials occur. In these cases the use of a simple stress criterion is not appropriate. The stress gradient has to be taken into account. Therefore, several approaches exist. The Theory of Critical Distances (TCD), as proposed by Taylor, summarizes all non-local approaches where the stresses are evaluated in a certain distance away from the stress concentration or criteria based on linear elastic fracture mechanics where the existence of an inherent flaw of a certain size is assumed. These approaches have in common that they are simple to use, but depend on a length scale with unclear physical meaning. Alternatively, Cohesive Zone Models (CZM), based on damage mechanics, are widely used. As the latter approach leads to a nonlinear problem the computational costs are high.

Besides the described approaches, Hashin [11] postulated the instantaneous formation of a finite sized crack an approach denoted as Finite Fracture Mechanics. Based on this

Figure 2: The temperature fields for co and counter gas flow operation (fuel gas methane) are depicted. The results were obtained by CFD-simulations and are provided by Forschungszentrum Jülich.

framework, Leguillon [9] proposed a coupled stress and energy criterion for the investigation of brittle fracture. It is postulated that two necessary and sufficient conditions in form of a stress and an energy criterion have to be fulfilled simultaneously. Evaluating the so-called coupled criterion only requires solving linear problems, which has a beneficial effect on the computing time. Moreover, only intrinsic material properties in terms of the strength and the fracture toughness are required. Finally, the failure load as well as the corresponding crack length are obtained by evaluating the coupled criterion.

Above the glass transition temperature, viscous material behavior occurs. Hence, stresses induced, for instance by differences in the coefficients of thermal expansion vanish after some time. But dead loads, as the weight of the stack, yield increasing deformations of the glass-ceramic seals. Since a material can not bear unlimited deformations, a crack may occur in the long run.

Figure 3: Deduction of the representative unit.

2. Mechanical and Numerical Modeling

In the following the mechanical model is introduced. It is assumed that the mechanical response of the stack does not depend on the out-of-plane direction x_3 . Especially, the temperature field (depicted in Fig. 2) only depends on the in-plane coordinates x_1 and x_2 . Based on the assumptions, only a representative unit consisting of two interconnects, the different layers of glass-ceramic seals and the metal frames, are further taken into account (Fig. 3 and Fig. 4).

Figure 4: Representative unit of the SOFC stack. In order to reduce the numerical effort the shown symmetry plane is used.

The weight on the top of the stack is considered in terms of a stress boundary condition. Furthermore, it is assumed that the thermal stresses within the representative unit are zero at the joining temperature of 1073 K. The representative unit, shown in Fig. 4 is modeled in the commercial finite element software *Abaqus*. The symmetry with respect to the x_1 - x_3 -plane is used in order to reduce the numerical effort by half. The finite element model is fully parameterized using a *Python* script. The model contains about 4.000.000 degrees of freedom and is discretized using fully integrated three-dimensional brick elements with bi-quadratic shape functions. The discretization is shown exemplarily in Fig. 5. Within the three-dimensional finite element model linear elasticity is presumed.

Figure 5: Discretization of the repeating unit (second interconnect is not depicted). The seals are shown in red, the interconnect and frames are grey.

3. Results

In the following, the stresses obtained by the three-dimensional finite element analyses are discussed. Three different mechanisms are responsible for the occurring stresses: the inhomogeneous temperature field, a mismatch in the coefficients of thermal expansion between the glass-ceramic sealant and the steel components (interconnect and frames), and the dead load in terms of the weight on the top of the stack. The obtained results are shown exemplarily in Fig. 6 for sealing 2.

Figure 6: The interlaminar (out-of-plane) stress components are depicted exemplarily for sealing 2.

It can be observed that stress concentrations at the junctions of the adjacent layers occur (so-called free-edge effect). Following elasticity theory the stresses become theoretically infinite at the junction. The reason for the observed behavior is the mismatch of the elastic constants between the sealant and the steel components. Besides the mismatch in elastic constants, also geometric discontinuities like corners cause stress concentrations as shown exemplarily for parallel gas flow. Moreover, for both load cases it can be observed the higher the temperature gradient the higher the stresses.

4. Sealing Failure Assessment

It has to be distinguished whether the temperature is above or below the glass transition temperature. For the investigated structural situation, both cases occur simultaneously as the glass transition temperature is about 873 K to 1053 K [12]. In the following both cases are discussed. Therefore, a minimal example is used in order to examine the elementary physical effects. In Fig. 7 the minimal example in form of a finite element model is depicted.

Figure 7: The finite element model for the used minimal example is shown. The glass-ceramic seal is shown in green and the steel components are grey.

4.1 Failure assessment for $T < T_g$

As shown exemplarily in Fig. 6, the stresses within the seals are highly inhomogeneous. Hence, the evaluation of a simple stress criterion is not sufficient. Instead, the coupled stress and energy criterion within the framework of finite fracture mechanics is employed. The solution of the coupled criterion in form of a quadratic interaction relation for the stresses and a linear interaction relation for the energy criterion is shown in Fig. 8.

8: Coupled stress and energy criterion. If both criteria are fulfilled simultaneously failure in form of instantaneous crack formation occurs. In the depicted case is the critical temperature difference at failure $\Delta T_f = -768$ K.

In the minimal example a rather high temperature difference is required for failure. Thus, it is expected that failure does not actually occur in operation. However, cooling down to

room temperature may lead to brittle fracture within the glass-ceramic seals since the temperature difference is of the same magnitude as the critical temperature difference predicted by the coupled criterion.

4.2 Failure assessment for $T > T_g$

For areas where the temperature is higher than the glass transition temperature viscous effects may play a fundamental role for failure. Especially, if the failure occurs not instantaneously but after a certain time viscous effects should be considered. On the one hand it is expected, that stress concentrations induced by differences in the coefficients of thermal expansion of the involved materials, the inhomogeneous temperature field or geometric discontinuities decrease due to viscous relaxation processes. On the other hand, dead loads as the weight on the top of the SOFC stack yield shear deformations. The shear deformations increase continuously over time. If the shear deformations exceed the deformability of the glass-ceramic sealant cracks can occur.

Figure 9: Development of the interlaminar stress components with respect to the time assuming viscous material behavior. The stresses are induced only by the differences in the coefficients of thermal expansion. The stress boundary condition, representing the weight on the top of the SOFC stack is neglected.

In Fig. 9 the development of selected interlaminar stress components is depicted. Due to the viscous relaxation the stresses are reduced over the time. This behavior can be used selectively to reduce the stresses and this is the reason why an operating temperature above the glass transition temperature of the glass-ceramic sealant is recommended in literature. However, this recommendation is based on an incomplete consideration. In Fig. 10 an example of creep deformation is shown.

Figure 10: The creep deformation of the glass-ceramic seal is shown with respect to the time. The deformation is induced by the dead load on the top of the SOFC stack.

An unlimited increasing creep deformation is observed. If the viscous material behavior is known exactly, a prediction of creep failure seems to be possible.

As a consequence, the recommendation of viscoelastic seals should be viewed with skepticism. The viscous behavior necessarily has to be taken into account as possible failure mode.

5. Conclusion

In the present work a methodology for the assessment of sealing failure in SOFC applications has been proposed. It has to be distinguished whether the operating temperature is above or below the glass transition temperature as the mechanical properties of the sealant change significantly reaching this critical value.

Below that temperature the sealant behaves brittle but occurring stresses are unequally distributed yielding highly localized stress concentrations. Hence, for the assessment of failure below the glass transition temperature the coupled stress and energy criterion is the method of choice. It provides the critical temperature at crack initiation as well as the corresponding crack length. The investigation revealed that for the underlying SOFC design no brittle failure has to be expected for areas where the operating temperature is below the glass transition temperature. But if the SOFC stack is cooled-down to room temperature brittle failure seems to be in reach. For that load case further investigations are recommended.

As the operating temperature is locally above the glass transition temperature, viscous effects have to be considered. Besides the advantageous relaxation of local stress concentrations dead loads as the weight of the SOFC stack and the internal pressure within the manifold yield increasing deformations over time. Those creep deformations can exceed the deformability of the glass ceramics sealant. As a consequence, creep failure may occur after some time.

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